

A program to insert interface elements in existing meshes

Zoutendijk J.B.M., J.B.M.Zoutendijk@student.tudelft.nl
Liaudat J., J.Liaudat@tudelft.nl
Dieudonné A.C., A.A.M.Dieudonne@tudelft.nl

Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands.

Abstract:

A program has been developed to insert interface elements in existing conventional 2D meshes. The program can be used to insert the new 9-node Pneumo-Hydro-Mechanical zero-thickness interface elements (PHMI) [1] in meshes consisting of solid 6 or 8-node MWAT2 elements and 3-node LICHA line elements. The PHMI elements can be inserted between solid elements of one element group, or along the boundaries between elements of two different element groups (Figure 1). In addition, FAIN2D elements and foundations can be added between elements of two different element groups.

Figure 1: PHMI elements introduced in conventional Finite Element mesh.

The program is written in Fortran with a Graphic User Interface (GUI) created with Python using the PYSimpleGui package. The GUI is used to instruct where and what kind of interface elements should be inserted. The algorithms implemented are adapted from those proposed by Nguyen [2] for purely mechanical double-node interface elements.

References:

- [1] Liaudat, J., Dieudonné, A.C., Vardon, P.J. (2022). Modelling gas fracturing in saturated clay using triple-node zero-thickness interface elements. *Under Review*
- [2] Nguyen, V.P. (2014). An open source program to generate zero-thickness cohesive interface elements. *Advances in Engineering Software*, 74:27-39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2014.04.002>.